

A Spatial Analysis of British Public House Names

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Summary

This paper explores patterns in the naming of public houses in Great Britain. In particular it examines spatial patterns in the term used to reference a pub such as ‘Inn’ or ‘Bar.’ It then goes on to explore the spatial linkages between pub names and other geographical features, particularly railway infrastructure and cathedrals. Patterns in pub naming are modelled via Gaussian processes embedded in binomial and multinomial regression models. Our intention is to try to make this reasonably close to something Martin Charlton would regard as an ideal talk, as it concerns spatial data analysis, pubs, trains and cathedrals.

KEYWORDS: Spatial autocorrelation, Spatial homogeneity, Gaussian process, Textual analysis, Pubs.

1 Introduction

This is a short paper illustrating how spatial data visualisation and analysis can be used to explore patterns in the naming of pubs in Britain. It draws on a number of computational tools including those for spatial data modelling, visualisation and text processing, all of which are available in R. The focus here is mainly exploratory, although some hypothesis testing and modelling is considered. As well as identifying trends in the naming of pubs spatial patterns are also identified, where certain pub names or more general styles in pub naming are clustered around certain parts of the country.

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2 Data source

The data here was obtained from <https://www.getthedata.com/open-pubs> - a web portal for a number of data sets created from open data providers - some are mixtures from more than one provider. This data comes from the Food Standard Agency's Food Hygiene Ratings (<https://ratings.food.gov.uk/open-data/>) and the ONS Postcode Directory (<https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk>). It is a data frame with columns as listed in table 1.

Field Name	Possible Values	Comments
<code>fsa_id</code>	int	Food Standard Agency's ID for this pub.
<code>name</code>	string	Name of the pub.
<code>address</code>	string	Address fields separated by commas.
<code>postcode</code>	string	Postcode of the pub.
<code>easting</code>	int	X coordinate of pub. GB National grid.
<code>northing</code>	int	Y coordinate of pub. GB National grid.
<code>latitude</code>	decimal	Latitude
<code>longitude</code>	decimal	Longitude
<code>local_authority</code>	string	Local authority this pub falls under.

Table 1. Variables provided in FSA data set

There is some redundancy here; the `easting` and `northing` variable pair and the `latitude` and `longitude` pair both contain point locations for each of the pubs. This table can be represented as a point 'SimpleFeatures' spatial data object. Also used - and obtained from <https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk> is a set of boundaries for counties and unitary authorities in the UK. In figure 1 the locations of the pubs (as points) are drawn over county boundaries with an alpha value of 0.02 - giving an overview of their geographical distribution.

3 A Visual Exploration

This exploration will consider different the words used in the names of pubs, and their relative popularity throughout England, Scotland and Wales. A simple way to consider this is to map the most commonly occurring words in pub names by local authority in Great Britain. This can be achieved in R by making use of the `tidytext` and `stringr` libraries. Together, these tools can remove *stopwords* from pub names - these are words such as 'the,' 'and,' 'of' and so on which appear very commonly in all types of speech and text, but convey little contextual information, and then count the number of occurrences of each word in the name of each pub. The counting is done on separately for each local authority, and the results are mapped in figure 2. From this is can be seen that most of the popular words are terms for a pub - such as 'inn,' 'bar' and 'hotel' - the later often used when an establishment primarily functions as a pub, but does also offer guest rooms. Some spatial patterns are apparent, perhaps most notably that popularity of the term 'bar' seems to cluster in Scottish local authorities, whereas in much of England and Wales 'inn' is more popular. In England places where 'bar' is more popular tend to be in urban areas, such as some of the London boroughs - and also in Tyne and Wear. There is also a strip from a little north of

Figure 1: Locations of pubs in Great Britain

London through Cambridge and into East Anglia, where the word ‘house’ is popular.

Some further explorations can also be carried out. For example a number of British pubs have the word ‘king,’ ‘queen,’ ‘prince’ or ‘princess’ in the title. It may be interesting to investigate this spatial distribution. An initial exploration here detected any pub names containing ‘king,’ ‘queen’ ‘prince’ or ‘princess.’ From the full sample of 41127 pubs, there are 1394 containing these words. A simple visualisation is to draw a dot map of the locations of the subset, and compare this to a dot map of the complementary set (ie non-royal pub names). Each dot map draws the dots with a degree of transparency so that areas of higher density can be seen. For the complementary subset dot map, a random subsample of the same size as the number of royal named pubs is used, so that intensity levels of the dot maps are comparable. This is shown in figure 3.

Although in general the dot patterns reflect urban areas, differences in intensity are noticeable - in particular ‘Royal’ pubs are more prevalent in East Anglia, and less so in North East England.

4 A Statistical Analysis Example

This can be analysed in more detail. A possible model for this is to consider a binary variable `royal` for each pub in the data set, where a value of 1 implies ‘king,’ ‘queen’ or ‘prince’ or ‘princess’ or ‘royal’ in the title, and a value of zero implies none of these words appear. A statistical model of the form

$$\text{Royal} \sim \text{Binomial}(\theta(x, y))$$

is proposed where (x, y) are the easting and northing of the pubs location. Mapping $\theta(x, y)$ gives an indication of regional trends in the likelihood of a pub have a royal-themed name. Here, a non-parametric approach is taken, where

$$\text{logit}(\theta(x, y)) = f(x, y)$$

and the function f is generated by a Gaussian process. The Gaussian process part of the model is similar to the assumptions made about the underlying trend surface being estimated using Kriging (Wackernagel 2003).

Here, the model is calibrated using the `gam` function in the R package `mgcv` (Wood 2003). Once calibrated, the value of $\theta(x, y)$ can be sampled at points on a hexagonal lattice, and mapped to visualise the underlying pattern - this is done in figure 4.

The shows that the probability that a pub name contains a royal word varies from around 0.01 to 0.08. There is generally a trend away from royal names as one heads into Scotland - and a notable trend in favour of such names in s strip from the north of London into East Anglia. The latter was noticed in the dot plots shown earlier. This trend also coincides geographically with a trend in the general most popular words - where ‘inn’ sees less favour in a similar region stretching towards East Anglia. Also in common is the distinction between England and Scotland. Finally, the South

Figure 2: Most common word in pub name by Local Authority

Figure 3: Dot Density Maps for Pubs With 'Royal' Names vs. general distribution.

Figure 4: Gaussian Process-Based Trend Surface for Probability of a 'Royal' Pub Name

West of England shows a trend in favour of royal names, and to a lesser extent so does the North West.

Finally, the validity of the trend surface can be considered, by comparing the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Akaike 1974) of the Gaussian process model to the ‘benchmark’ model where $\theta(x, y)$ is a constant. Doing this, we have

Model	AIC	Δ AIC
Benchmark	1723.2	178.6
Gaussian Process	1544.6	

Table 2. AIC values for the Gaussian and Benchmark Models

Thus, the AIC of the Gaussian process model is considerably lower than that of the benchmark model, suggesting it has notably better prediction power.

5 Trains, Stations and Pub Names

A further geographical factor which could influence public house names is their geographical nearness to a railway line, or a railway station. Geographical data (in the form of shapefiles) is available for both train tracks and railway station locations from <https://data.gov.uk>. In conjunction with the existing pub data, two questions are investigated:

1. Are pubs with railway themed names closer to railway stations?
2. Are pubs with railway themed names closer to railway tracks?

Here, a railway-themed name is one containing at least one of the words *Railway, station, train* or *locomotive*. The distribution of distances to stations and tracks for railway themed pub names and others is shown in Figure 5. From this, although it is clear that many non-railway themed pubs are close to stations or tracks, the distribution for railway themed pubs suggests suggests a tendency to be closer.

This relationship can be modelled: if θ is the probability that a pub has a railway themed name, and d is the distance to that pub’s closest railway station, then

$$\text{logit}(\theta(d)) = f(d)$$

- where f is generated by a 1d Gaussian process

Fitting this model gives the result in figure 6.

Figure 7 shows the result of a similar model, but this time d is the distance to railway tracks. In both cases, although a relatively small proportion of pubs actually have railway-themed names, this proportion decreases with distance.

Finally, a similar analysis can be applied to the nearness of cathedrals to church-themed pub names, using data relating to cathedrals in the UK (pers. comm.) Here, ‘church-themed’ is defined as

Figure 5: Distance to Railway Stations and Tracks

Figure 6: Probability of a railway themed pub name vs. distance to station

Figure 7: Probability of a railway themed pub name vs. distance to railway track

Figure 8: Probability of a church themed pub name vs. distance to cathedral

containing the words *bishop*, *mitre*, *cathedral*, *minster* and *abbey*. A similar curve fitting analysis is shown in figure 8.

It seems that railway stations have a stronger influence on pub names than cathedrals...

(1537 words)

6 Closing Comments

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